

Stability Constant of Silver Diethyldithiocarbamate in 75% Ethyl Alcohol (Leden Method)

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The stability constant of silver diethyldithiocarbamate complex has been determined potentiometrically employing Leden's method. The value is found to be 1.0×10^9 in 75% ethyl alcohol.

In the present work, the stability constant of silver diethyldithiocarbamate in 75% ethyl alcohol has been determined using Leden's method.¹ Silver electrode was a pure silver wire cleansed with dilute nitric acid and then washed with water. SCE in conjunction with KNO_3 salt bridge was used as the reference electrode. The following cells (A and B) were set up.

The ionic strength was maintained at 0.01 *M* by adding KNO_3 . The e.m.f. of various mixtures were noted employing Mullard potentiometer bridge reading upto $\pm 2\text{mV}$. The results are given in Table 1.

The e.m.f. of cell of type B containing sodium diethyldithiocarbamate (NaDDC) is given by

$$E_2 = E' + \frac{RT}{nF} \ln (M)$$

where (*M*) is the free metal ion concentration. In the above equation *E'* includes the potential of the calomel electrode, the liquid junction potential and the correction term for activity coefficient in mixed solvents. All the above factors were kept constant in measuring the e.m.f. of the cell. In case of cell A, i.e., when no ligand is added, the e.m.f. of the cell is given by

$$E_1 = E' + \frac{RT}{nF} \ln (C_M)$$

TABLE I

Vol. of 0.0025 *M* AgNO₃, 0.8 ml.; 0.1 *M* KNO₃, 2 ml. and ethanol 15 ml.

Sl. No.	0.01 <i>M</i> NaDDC (ml.)	H ₂ O (ml.)	e.m.f. (V)
1	0.0	2.2	0.345
2	0.1	2.1	0.325
3	0.2	2.0	0.213
4	0.4	1.8	0.068
5	0.6	1.6	-0.092
6	0.8	1.4	-0.190
7	1.0	1.2	-0.252
8	1.2	1.0	-0.277
9	1.4	0.8	-0.273
10	1.6	0.6	-0.299
11	1.8	0.4	-0.306
12	2.0	0.2	-0.312

where (*C_M*) is the metal ion concentration. When ligand is added some of the metal ions are involved in complex formation and a new potential say *E*₂, will be set up. Hence,

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta E = E_1 - E_2 &\approx \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \left(\frac{C_M}{M} \right) \\ &= \frac{0.059}{n} \log \left(\frac{C_M}{M} \right) \text{ at } 25^\circ.\end{aligned}$$

The quantity (*C_M/M*) is the inverse of the degree of the formation and is designated as ϕ so that,

$$\log \phi = \frac{nF}{2.303 RT} \cdot \Delta E$$

According to Leden¹

$$F_1(L) = \frac{(C_M/M) - 1}{(L)} = B_1 + B_2(L) + B_3(L)^2 \dots + B_n(L)^{n-1}$$

where $B_1 = K_1$, $B_2 = K_1 K_2$, ... $B_n = K_1 \cdot K_2 \dots K_n$, K_1, K_2 etc., are the stepwise stability constants and (*L*) is the concentration of free ligand. From the above equation it is easy to calculate $F_1(L)$ (Table 2).

TABLE 2

Values of functions used in the calculation of stability constants

Sl. No.*	E	(C _M /M)	F ₁ (L)	(L) × 10 ⁴
4	0.277	5.901 × 10 ⁴	5.90 × 10 ⁹	1
5	0.437	3.365 × 10 ⁷	1.68 × 10 ²¹	2
6	0.535	1.637 × 10 ⁹	5.46 × 10 ¹²	3
7	0.597	1.905 × 10 ¹⁰	4.76 × 10 ¹³	4
8	0.622	5.128 × 10 ¹⁰	1.02 × 10 ¹⁴	5
9	0.618	4.265 × 10 ¹⁰	7.27 × 10 ¹³	6
10	0.644	1.280 × 10 ¹¹	1.76 × 10 ¹⁴	7
11	0.651	1.622 × 10 ¹¹	2.02 × 10 ¹⁴	8
12	0.657	2.089 × 10 ¹¹	2.32 × 10 ¹⁴	9

* Numbers correspond to those given in Table 1.

On plotting $F_1(L)$ and on extrapolation to zero concentration of ligand, the stability constant of silver complex is obtained. It is found to be 1.0×10^9 .

In view of the single stability constant a somewhat awkward situation arises as to the structure of the complex. The two following structures of similar complexes have been quoted in the literature, though without adequate evidence.

(B^a)

A comparable structure,

is, therefore, proposed although many authors have pointed out that bidentate ligands like ethylenediamine do not form chelate complexes with silver atom^{4,5,6}.

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